

Metal complexes of unsaturated diketoanilides

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Abstract : A new series of diketoanilides, in which the keto groups are attached to olefinic linkages, have been synthesized and characterized. Their IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data revealed that only one of the carbonyl groups is enolised and engaged in intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Neutral bidentate coordination of these compounds with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} has been established on the basis of analytical and spectral data.

Keywords : Unsaturated diketoanilides, metal complexes, IR spectra, NMR spectra, mass spectra.

Numerous reports exist on the synthesis, characterization and applications of metal complexes of β-ketoanilides such as acetoacetanilides where the keto group attached to alkyl/aryl functions. However, no systematic investigation appeared on β-ketoanilides in which the keto group linked to olefinic linkage. In recent years such 'unsaturated' β-dicarbonyl compounds and their metal complexes have gained considerable importance mainly because of the observation that the active constituents of several traditional medicinal plants contain such compounds¹⁻⁸. A typical example is curcuminoids, the active chemical constituents of turmeric, (*Curcuma longa*, Linn., *Zingiberaceae* family) and their metal complexes. Therefore, synthesis and characterization of such unsaturated carbonyl systems and their metal complexes have tremendous importance. In this paper we report the preparation and characterization of a

new series of 'unsaturated' diketoanilides and their typical metal complexes.

Results and discussion

A well established synthetic route to 'unsaturated' β-dicarbonyl compounds is based on the synthesis of curcuminoids by Pabon⁷ using the reaction of aromatic aldehydes and β-dicarbonyl compounds containing at least one acetyl group in presence of boric oxide, tri(sec-butyl) borate and n-butylamine. The use of boric oxide and tri(sec-butyl)borate is to prevent Knoevenagel type condensation and facilitate Claisen type condensation by the formation of a boron complex of the diketone. However, in the present study when acetoacetanilide was employed as the dicarbonyl compound two products 1 and 2 (Scheme 1) were formed probably due to the electronic effects of the amide carbonyl.

Table 1. Analytical and IR spectral data of the unsaturated diketoanilides

Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Mol. Wt. ^a Found (Calcd.)	Elemental analysis (%) :			IR bands (cm ⁻¹)		
				Found (Calcd.)			v(C=O) amide I	v(C=O) olefinic	v(C=O) cinnamoyl
L ¹ (C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃)	30	110	425 (424)	76.34 (76.42)	5.62 (5.66)	6.71 (6.60)	1721s	1659s	1619s
L ² (C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃)	28	88	473 (474)	78.30 (78.48)	5.48 (5.49)	5.78 (5.91)	1718s	1660s	1618s
L ³ (C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄)	32	56	413 (414)	72.34 (72.46)	5.24 (5.31)	6.74 (6.76)	1718s	1660s	1620s
L ⁴ (C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄)	34	110	438 (440)	73.49 (73.64)	5.40 (5.45)	6.31 (6.36)	1716s	1668s	1620s
L ⁵ (C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄)	32	106	489 (490)	75.90 (75.92)	5.28 (5.31)	5.70 (5.71)	1720s	1665s	1618s

^aRast's method.

Table 2. ¹H NMR and mass spectral data of the unsaturated diketoanilides

Compd	¹ H NMR (δ, ppm)					Mass spectral data (<i>m/z</i>)
	Enolic OH	NH	Methine	Methylene	Phenolic OH	
L ¹ (C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃)	13 178	10 103 9 876	5 970	3 585	–	424, 347, 332, 323, 304, 293, 290, 279, 270, 262, 240, 162, 145, 134, 131, 120, 103
L ² (C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃)	12 502	9 993 9 776	5 890	3 502	–	474, 397, 382, 354, 347, 340, 323, 320, 312, 293, 290, 279, 195, 181, 162, 134, 127, 120
L ³ (C ₂₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄)	12 140	9 981 9 802	6 002	3 587	–	414, 347, 337, 323, 322, 294, 293, 280, 279, 260, 252, 230, 162, 135, 134, 121, 120
L ⁴ (C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄)	13 426	9 992 9 789	5 968	3 591	10 158	440, 363, 348, 347, 323, 320, 306, 293, 286, 279, 278, 256, 162, 161, 147, 134, 120, 119
L ⁵ (C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄)	13 234	9 983 9 838	5 896	3 570	10 212	490, 413, 398, 370, 356, 347, 336, 328, 323, 306, 293, 279, 211, 197, 169, 162, 143, 134, 120

Table 3. Physical and analytical data of metal complexes of the unsaturated diketoanilides

Complex	M p (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%)			
			Found (Calcd)			
			C	H	N	M
[NiL ¹ (OAc) ₂]	204	75	61 92 (61 93)	4 87 (4 99)	4 68 (4 66)	9 81 (9 77)
C ₃₁ H ₃₀ N ₂ NiO ₇						
[NiL ² (OAc) ₂]	198	72	64 58 (64 54)	4 94 (4 92)	4 31 (4 30)	9 10 (9 02)
C ₃₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ NiO ₇						
[NiL ³ (OAc) ₂]	186	74	58 64 (58 91)	4 76 (4 74)	4 75 (4 74)	9 80 (9 94)
C ₂₉ H ₂₈ N ₂ NiO ₈						
[NiL ⁴ (OAc) ₂]	190	68	60 30 (60 32)	4 84 (4 86)	4 60 (4 54)	9 54 (9 52)
C ₃₁ H ₃₀ N ₂ NiO ₈						
[NiL ⁵ (OAc) ₂]	188	66	62 90 (63 00)	4 79 (4 80)	4 18 (4 20)	8 80 (8 81)
C ₃₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ NiO ₈						
[CuL ¹ (OAc) ₂]	174	65	61 12 (61 43)	5 04 (4 95)	4 70 (4 62)	10 43 (10 49)
C ₃₁ H ₃₀ CuN ₂ O ₇						
[CuL ² (OAc) ₂]	178	68	64 01 (64 07)	4 74 (4 88)	4 22 (4 27)	9 77 (9 69)
C ₃₅ H ₃₂ CuN ₂ O ₇						
[CuL ³ (OAc) ₂]	194	74	58 14 (58 43)	4 65 (4 70)	4 69 (4 70)	10 84 (10 67)
C ₂₉ H ₂₈ CuN ₂ O ₈						
[CuL ⁴ (OAc) ₂]	166	70	59 74 (59 85)	4 80 (4 83)	4 54 (4 50)	10 24 (10 22)
C ₃₁ H ₃₀ CuN ₂ O ₈						
[CuL ⁵ (OAc) ₂]	178	72	62 46 (62 54)	4 74 (4 77)	4 16 (4 17)	9 50 (9 46)
C ₃₅ H ₃₂ CuN ₂ O ₈						
[ZnL ¹ (OAc) ₂]	144	78	60 99 (61 25)	4 90 (4 94)	4 59 (4 61)	10 64 (10 76)
C ₃₁ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₇ Zn						
[ZnL ² (OAc) ₂]	162	76	63 98 (63 89)	4 85 (4 88)	4 28 (4 27)	9 82 (9 69)
C ₃₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₇ Zn						
[ZnL ³ (OAc) ₂]	150	74	59 54 (58 25)	4 64 (4 69)	4 67 (4 69)	10 90 (10 94)
C ₂₉ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₈ Zn						
[ZnL ⁴ (OAc) ₂]	156	68	59 54 (59 67)	4 92 (4 81)	4 41 (4 49)	10 44 (10 49)
C ₃₁ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₈ Zn						
[ZnL ⁵ (OAc) ₂]	164	66	62 39 (62 37)	4 73 (4 75)	4 13 (4 16)	9 63 (9 71)
C ₃₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₈ Zn						

On column chromatographic separation about 30% of the unsaturated diketoanilide **2** was obtained. The compounds are stable, show sharp melting points and are soluble in common organic solvents. Elemental analysis, IR

(Table 1), ¹H NMR and mass spectral data (Table 2) of the compounds are in agreement with structure **2**. These compounds formed well defined and crystalline complexes with acetates of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} ions. The observed C, H, N

and metal percentages suggest $[ML(OAc)_2]$ stoichiometry of the complexes (Table 3). All metal complexes are non-electrolytes in DMF (specific conductance $<10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $10^{-3} M$ solution). The Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} chelates are diamagnetic while Cu^{II} complexes showed normal paramagnetic moment. The observed IR, 1H NMR and mass spectra of the complexes are fully consistent with the structure 3.

Infrared spectra : Acetoacetanilide exist predominantly in the keto form⁹ and the most characteristic bands in the region $1650\text{--}1800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to the amide carbonyl at $\sim 1667 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and acetyl carbonyl at $\sim 1720 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ^{10,11}. The spectra of all the unsaturated diketoanilides show three strong bands at ~ 1720 , ~ 1660 and $\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable respectively to the stretching of the amide carbonyl (amide I), alkenyl carbonyl and the partially enolised cinnamoyl carbonyl functions of structure 2. Spectra of the compounds in the region below 1600 cm^{-1} show several medium intensity bands due to various C=C and C-N stretching vibrations and to N-H, N=C=O bending, etc. IR spectra of all the compounds showed a prominent band at $\sim 970 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ typical of *trans*-CH=CH- absorption. The broad band in the region $2800\text{--}3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests the existence of the compounds predominantly in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enolic form¹². This broad band remained almost unaffected in the IR spectra of the complexes, which indicate that the enolic OH is not replaced during complex formation. The band at $\sim 1720 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the free ligand disappeared in the spectra of all the complexes and instead a comparatively broad and intense band appeared at $\sim 1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The par-

tially enolised cinnamoyl carbonyl stretching of the free ligand at $\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ remained unaltered in the spectra of all the chelates. These indicate that the amide and alkenyl carbonyl groups are involved in coordination with the metal ion. Monodentate acetate usually show two bands at $\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to antisymmetric and symmetric stretching respectively¹³. Since carbonyl absorption of the compounds also appeared in this region the band at $\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ could not be located. However, a medium intensity band observed at $\sim 1320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggest the monodentate coordination of the acetate groups. That the carbonyl groups are involved in bonding with the metal as in structure 3 is further supported by the appearance of two medium intensity bands in the region $418\text{--}480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ν_{M-O} vibrations¹³. Thus IR spectra of the complexes support the neutral bidentate coordination of the unsaturated diketoanilides. Important bands that appeared in the spectra of complexes are given in Table 4.

1H NMR spectra : The 1H NMR spectra of the compounds displayed a one proton singlet at $\sim \delta$ 13 ppm due to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enolic proton^{14,15}. Signals at δ 10 ppm and δ 9.8 ppm indicate the different electronic environment of the two NH protons. The methine proton of structure 2 appeared at $\sim \delta$ 6 ppm and the aromatic protons in the range δ 7–8 ppm. The spectra of L^4 and L^5 displayed signals at δ 10.1 ppm and δ 10.2 ppm due to the phenolic OH groups. The assignments of various proton signals observed are assembled in Table 2. The enolic and NH proton signals of the free ligand remained almost unaffected in the 1H NMR spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} and

Table 4. Characteristic IR stretching bands and mass spectral data of the Cu^{II} complexes of the unsaturated diketoanilides

Complex	IR (cm^{-1})					Mass spectral data (m/z)
	(C=O) Cinnamoyl	(C=O) Metal chelated	(C=C) phenyl/ (C=C) alkenyl/ amide II	amide III, IV, V and VI	(M-O)	
$[CuL^1(OAc)_2]$ $C_{11}H_{10}CuN_2O_7$	1620s	1632s	1595m, 1545m, 1498m, 1530m	1248m, 656m, 693m, 617m	418m, 464m	607, 605, 548, 546, 515, 513, 489, 487, 424, 355, 353, 296, 294, 237, 235, 183, 181, 172, 162, 134, 120
$[CuL^2(OAc)_2]$ $C_{15}H_{12}CuN_2O_7$	1618s	1637s	1545m, 1516m, 1498m, 1516m	1238m, 654m, 691m, 604m	425m, 470m	657, 655, 598, 596, 565, 563, 474, 473, 471, 397, 312, 290, 183, 181, 162, 134, 127, 120
$[CuL^3(OAc)_2]$ $C_{29}H_{28}CuN_2O_8$	1619s	1640s	1580m, 1541m, 1498m, 1518m	1234m, 565m, 690m, 618m	426m, 480m	597, 595, 538, 536, 505, 503, 479, 477, 414, 413, 411, 337, 280, 252, 162, 134, 120
$[CuL^4(OAc)_2]$ $C_{11}H_{10}CuN_2O_8$	1620s	1642s	1599m, 1541m, 1494m, 1532m	1242m, 654m, 694m, 618m	418m, 472m	623, 621, 564, 562, 529, 531, 505, 503, 440, 439, 437, 363, 320, 278, 162, 161, 134, 120
$[CuL^5(OAc)_2]$ $C_{15}H_{12}CuN_2O_8$	1617s	1638s	1578m, 1540m, 1488m, 1522m	1230m, 652m, 692m, 616m	420m, 478m	673, 671, 614, 612, 581, 579, 555, 553, 490, 489, 487, 398, 356, 162, 143, 134, 120

Zn^{II} complexes indicating the non-involvement of these protons in complexation. Unlike in the spectra of the ligands, the complexes show a signal at $\sim\delta$ 2.5 ppm due to

methyl protons of acetate groups. That the phenolic OH group of L⁴ and L⁵ are not involved in bonding with the metal ion is clearly indicated in the spectra of their complexes where the phenolic signals remain unaltered.

Mass spectra : The formulation of the diketoanilides as in structure **2** is clearly supported from the presence of intense molecular ion peak in the mass spectra. Peaks due to [Ar-CH=CH-C=O]⁺, [Ar-CH=CH(C=O)-CH₂]⁺ and [P-C₆H₅NHCO]⁺ confirm the condensation of the γ -methyl group of acetacetanilide with aromatic aldehyde. Important fragments appeared in the spectra are given in Table 2. The FAB mass spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes show intense molecular ion peak due to [CuL(OAc)₂]. Peaks due to the removal of one or both acetate groups, [CuL]⁺ and L⁺ are characteristic of all the spectra. The spectra of all the chelates contain a number of fragments containing copper in the 3 : 1 natural abundance of ⁶³Cu and ⁶⁵Cu isotopes. Important fragments appeared in the spectra are given in Table 4.

ESR spectra : The ESR spectra of the copper(II) complexes of L¹ and L² were recorded at 77 K in DMF solution. The observed *g* and *A* values (Table 5) are comparable to that reported for copper acetoacetanilide^{16,17}. This suggests the presence of appreciable delocalisation in the chelate ring.

Table 5. ESR parameters of some Cu^{II} complexes in DMF at 77 K

Cu ^{II} complexes of	<i>g</i>	<i>g</i> _⊥	<i>A</i> × 10 ⁻⁴ (cm ⁻¹)	<i>A</i> _⊥ × 10 ⁻⁴ (cm ⁻¹)
L ¹	2.268	2.051	156	45.5
L ²	2.260	2.058	161	44.2

Electronic spectra : The UV spectra of the diketoanilides show two broad bands with maxima at \sim 380 nm and \sim 260 nm due to the various $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The absorption maxima of the metal chelates bear close resemblance with the free ligands which indicates that no structural alteration of the ligand has occurred during complexation. However, the values shifted slightly to longer wavelength in the spectra of the metal complexes indicating the involvement of the carbonyl group in metal complexation. In the copper(II) complexes the presence of a broad visible band at \sim 15000 cm⁻¹ and the measured μ_{eff} values (1.75–1.81 B.M.) support the square-planar structure¹⁸. The observed diamagnetism and broad medium-intensity band at \sim 17800 cm⁻¹ in the visible spectra of the nickel(II) chelates undoubtedly suggest their square-planar

geometry. In conformity, visible spectra of the chelates in pyridine solution (10⁻³ M) showed three bands corresponding to configurational change from square planar to octahedral due to the association of pyridine. The three well-separated absorption bands at λ_{max} \sim 8234, \sim 13556 and \sim 24349 cm⁻¹ correspond to the transitions ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (*F*) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (*P*), respectively.

Antifungal studies : Unsaturated β -dicarbonyl compounds such as curcuminoids are known to possess antifungal and antimicrobial activities in addition to their numerous biological significance¹⁻⁵. Since the unsaturated β -ketoanilides are structurally related to curcuminoids, the antifungal activity of these compounds and their typical metal complexes were also studied by disk diffusion technique.

The three different fungal strains used are *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus parasiticus* and *Rhizopus oryzae*¹⁹. The results reveal that the compounds possess significant activity against all the tested organism and the free ligands exhibited more activity than their metal complexes. L⁴ and L⁵ which possess an -OH group in the aromatic ring show maximum activity.

Experimental

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen percentages were determined by micro analyses (Heraeus Elemental analyzer) at CDRI, Lucknow and metal contents by AAS (Perkin-Elmer 2380). The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded in methanol solution (10^{-4} M) on a 1601 Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr discs) on a 8101 Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆) on a Varian 300 NMR spectrometer, ESR spectra (X-band) at 77 K using a Varian E 112 ESR spectrometer and mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol/SX-102 mass spectrometer (FAB using Argon and *meta*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix). Molar conductance of the complexes was determined in DMF at 28 ± 1 °C using solution of about 10^{-3} M concentration. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on a Guoy type magnetic balance.

Synthesis of unsaturated diketoanilides : The aldehydes used for the preparation of unsaturated diketoanilides are benzaldehyde, naphthalene-1-carbaldehyde, furfural, 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 2-hydroxynaphthalene-1-carbaldehyde. A mixture of acetoacetanilide (1.77 g, 0.01 mol) and boric oxide (0.35 g, 0.005 mol) in dry ethylacetate was stirred on a magnetic stirrer for about 1 h. To this, a solution of aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) and tri(*sec*-butyl)borate (4.6 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in dry ethylacetate (~15 mL) was added and stirred for ~5 h with the slow addition of *n*-butylamine (0.5 mL in 5 mL dry ethylacetate) and the reaction mixture was kept overnight. Hot (~70 °C) HCl (0.4 M, 7.5 mL) was added and again stirred for ~1 h. The mixture was extracted repeatedly with ethylacetate and the combined extracts were evaporated to dryness on a water bath to get a pasty mass. To this 10 mL of 2 M HCl was added and kept for ~24 h. The solution was stirred well and the precipitate formed was filtered. The tlc of the products revealed the presence of two compounds and were quantitatively separated by column chromatography as outlined below.

The crude product was dissolved in minimum quantity of dry ethylacetate and placed over a column (2 × 100 cm) densely packed with silica-gel (mesh 60–120) and eluted with 3 : 5 v/v chloroform-acetone mixture at a uniform flow rate of 2 mL per min. As the elution proceeds, two bands were developed in the column, a pale yellow lower band and an orange red upper band. The lower region on evaporation gave the pure unsaturated β-ketoanilide 1. The upper region was collected as 10 mL aliquots in separate tubes and in each case the purity was established by tlc. The combined eluates on evaporation gave the pure unsaturated diketoanilide 2.

Synthesis of metal complexes : To a refluxing solution of the compound in ethanol (0.001 mol, 20 mL) an aqueous solution of metal(II) acetate (0.001 mol, 15 mL) was added drop by drop with stirring. The pH of the solution was adjusted around 6 using sodium acetate and refluxing was continued for ~4 h. The solution was concentrated to half the volume and then cooled in ice. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed several times with water, then with ethanol, and recrystallised from hot methanol and dried in vacuum.

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